

Polarographic Investigations on the Kinetics of Discharge of Cadmium (II) and Nickel (II) at D.M.E. in 3-Mercapto, 1-2 Propanediol Media

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The reduction of cadmium (II) and Nickel (II) at the dropping mercury electrode, studied in KNO_3 -MPD (MPD refers to 3-mercapto-1, 2-propanediol) mixtures at constant ionic strength (0.5μ), have been found to be irreversible. Kinetics of the electrode reaction has been investigated and the values of kinetic parameters (transfer coefficient α and forward rate constant $K_{f,h}^\circ$) have been calculated by Koutecky's theoretical treatment as extended by Meites and Israel.

Mercapto compounds containing active -SH and -COOH groups have a wide variety of applications varying from biological, pharmaceutical, analytical and other chemical uses and have been reported to form complexes with some metals and hence the importance of this class of compounds has grown. The polarographic behaviour of several such compounds viz., Thiomalic Acid¹, β -mercapto propionic acid², thiolactic acid³ and 3-mercapto-1,2-propanediol⁴ and their metal complexes⁵⁻⁸ have already been studied in these laboratories by Saxena and Coworkers and yielded useful results. 3-mercapto, 1-2 propanediol has been used (a) as stabilizing agent in acronitrile polymers⁹⁻¹⁰, thiamine¹¹ and antibiotic solutions¹², (b) in polymerization and copolymerization of acronitrile and (c) as an analytical reagent for the determination of palladium¹⁴ spectrophotometrically. In view of its importance, it was considered worthwhile to study its complexation behaviour with cadmium and nickel for which no reference could be traced out in the literature.

Preliminary experiments pertaining to the nature of the cathodic waves showed that both Cd(II) and Ni(II) reduce irreversibly in 3-mercapto-1,2 propanediol medium. The complexation, therefore, could not be studied but the kinetics of their discharge at d.m.e. was undertaken employing Koutecky's¹⁵ method. The values of the transfer coefficient α , and forward rate constant $K_{f,h}^\circ$ have been computed at different concentrations of 3-mercapto-1,2, propanediol.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Mercapto-1,2-propaneodiol, assaying 90% was supplied by Evans Chemetics, Inc., N.Y. All other chemicals used, were either Anal-R, BDH grade or Merck's guaranteed extra pure reagents, which were used without further purification. Their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled air free conductivity water. Triton X-100 (0.001%) was used as maximum suppressor. The ionic strength was maintained 0.5 M by adding the requisite

amount of KNO_3 . Ammonia buffer ($0.4 \text{ M NH}_4\text{OH} + 0.4 \text{ mM NH}_4\text{NO}_3$) in case of nickel was used.

Polarographic measurements were performed with a Cambridge (G.P.) polarograph equipped with thermostated H-cell and saturated calomel electrode. Capillary had the following characteristics $m = 1.563 \text{ mg/sec}$, $t = 3.21 \text{ secs}$ at -1.20 volts (vs S.C.E.) in 0.5 M KNO_3 . Doubly distilled mercury was used for d.m.e. Unless otherwise stated all the measurements were done at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$, ($E_{1/2}$) S needed no correction as the cell had the resistance below 1000 ohms. Dissolved air was removed from the solution by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen through the cell and a complete inert atmosphere was maintained over the solution during electrolysis.

Logarithmic plots of a series of $c-v$ curves determined at different concentrations of metal and ligand yielded straight lines with different slopes deviating considerably from the theoretical value expected for one or two electron reductions and thus revealing the irreversible nature of the waves. Therefore, investigations were confined to the kinetic study of the electrode reactions.

Fig. 1. Plots of $E_{d.e.}$ as a function of $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ of Cd-MPD system at different concentrations of ligand: (1) 0.005 M , (2) 0.01 M , (3) 0.02 M .

Throughout the measurements, the current at the end of the drop life was recorded instead of the average current because the determination of kinetic parameters is based on the Koutecky's calculations which are more accurately reproduced by measuring the maximum current¹⁷. To determine the diffusion controlled nature of the wave, the polarograms were recorded at different heights of the mercury column. The kinetic parameters (transfer coefficient α and formal rate constant $K_{f,h}^0$) have been calculated by Koutecky's¹⁵ treatment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Both Cd^{++} and Ni^{++} produce a well defined single cathodic wave in 0.5 M KNO_3 as supporting electrolyte and 0.001% Triton X-100 as maximum suppressor. Due to complex formation the half wave potential values shift to the more negative potentials with the increase in concentration of MPD in case of Cd^{++} ion and the half wave potentials Ni^{++} ion has shifted markedly to the more positive value. The possible reason for the positive shift in the half wave potential may be due to the ion pair formation¹⁸. The plots of i_d as a function of square root of the height of mercury reservoir was found to be linear and passes through the origin, indicating that the reduction of Cd^{++} and Ni^{++} in MPD medium is diffusion controlled.

An analysis of the wave for the complexation (plot of $E_{d.e.}$ vs. $\log i/i_d - i$) was linear in all the cases (Fig. 1 and 2) but the theoretical slope indicating that the reduction is irreversible. The shape of the c-v curves remained well defined as the concentration of ligand is increased. The polarographic data obtained with 0.4 mM Cd⁺⁺ and Ni⁺⁺ in 0.001% Triton X-100, at ionic strength 0.5 M KNO₃ and different concentrations of ligand in ammonia buffer have been recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Shift in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of Cd (II) and Ni (II) on adding increasing concentration of MPD and values of αn and $K_{f,h}^\circ$

Cd-MPD system				Ni-MPD system			
Concn. of ligand	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	αn	$K_{f,h}^\circ$	Concn. of ligand	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	αn	$K_{f,h}^\circ$
0.005M	0.8548	0.76	2.295×10^{-10}	0.002M	1.004	0.242	5.864×10^{-6}
0.01 M	0.9123	0.68	4.392×10^{-10}	0.01 M	1.023	0.354	9.514×10^{-6}
0.02 M	0.9652	0.65	3.544×10^{-10}	0.02 M	1.028	0.384	9.328×10^{-6}

The kinetic parameters (the transfer coefficient α , and the formal rate constant $K_{f,h}^\circ$ at -0.2412 vs. S.C.E.) have been calculated by Koutecky's¹⁵ treatment as extended by Meites and Israel¹⁶ which is based on a plot of $E_{d.e.}$ vs. $\log i/i_d - i$ and may be constructed as for a reversible wave.

The mathematical solution for an electrode reaction at the d.m.e. controlled by the kinetics of electron transfer is given by

$$i/i_d = F(X) \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{where } X = (12/7)^{\frac{1}{2}} K_{f,h} \frac{t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots (2)$$

in which ' t ' is drop time, D_0 is the diffusion coefficient of electroactive substance, $K_{f,h}$ is the potential dependent heterogeneous rate constant described by

$$K_{f,h} = K_{f,h}^\circ \exp[-\alpha n F(E + 0.2412)/RT] \quad \dots (3)$$

where E is referred to S.C.E., ' i ' and ' i_d ' are the currents that actually flow at the end of the life of the drop at potential E and on the plateau of the wave respectively.

Fig. 2. Plots of $E_{d.e.}$ as a function of $\log \frac{i}{i_d} - i$ of Ni-MPD system at different concentrations of ligand:

(1) 0.002 M, (2) 0.01 M, (3) 0.02 M.

From the values of i/i_d at various selected potentials, the corresponding values of function 'X' may be obtained from the original table of Koutecky¹⁵. Plotting $\log X$ vs. $E_{d.e.}$ then permits values for $K_{f,h}^\circ$ and αn to be secured. For this purpose it is convenient to combine preceding equation into

$$\log_{10}(X) = \log_{10}(12/7)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{K_{f,h}^\circ t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{\alpha n F}{2 \cdot 303 RT} \quad \dots (4)$$

Thus a plot of $\log X$ vs. $E_{d.e.}$ shall be linear; $E = 0$ (vs. N.H.E. or -0.2412 vs. S.C.E.) the value of $K_{f,h}^\circ$ can be obtained. Meanwhile αn is obtained from the slope of the line.

The amount of labour involved in the process is excessive. Meites and Israel¹⁶ have shown that the labour can be considerably decreased by taking advantage of the fact that, for value of i/i_d between 0.1 to 0.95, Koutecky's values for X and i/i_d correspond to a linear relationship between $\log X$ and $i/(i_d - i)$. In this way the equation of a totally irreversible wave becomes at 25° .

$$E_{d.e.} + 0.2412 = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{f,h}^\circ t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)} \quad \dots (5)$$

which may be written as

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\text{with } E_{\frac{1}{2}} = -0.241/2 + \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{f,h}^\circ t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots (7)$$

In this equation both $E_{d.e.}$ and $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ are referred to S.C.E.

The kinetic parameters for Cd-MPD and Ni-MPD systems were calculated by using equations (6 & 7). The value of αn was obtained from slope = $-\frac{(0.0542)}{\alpha n}$ of the straight line of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)}$ (Fig. 1 & 2). The intercept of the same plot gave the value of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$, which was used to calculate $K_{f,h}^\circ$ after having the value of $D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}$ from the Ilkovic equation. The values of αn and $K_{f,h}^\circ$ calculated at different concentrations of ligand are tabulated (Table 1).

The present investigation thus shows that Cd^{++} and Ni^{++} reduce irreversibly in 3-mercapto-1,2 propanediol media at d.m.e. Hence the kinetic parameters (transfer coefficient α , and forward rate constant $K_{f,h}^\circ$ have been calculated by Koutecky's method.

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